

treatment, were applied at transplanting. The remaining three-fourths of the N was applied in three equal splits at tillering, maximum tillering, and panicle initiation. No irrigation was required because rainfall was sufficient from active tillering to crop maturity.

Significant differences were observed among genotypes and N levels for yield, N uptake, and net returns (see table). Genotype IET8002 gave significantly higher grain and straw yields than did the other

genotypes. In general, both yield and net return increased up to 120 kg N ha⁻¹.

Interaction effect of N levels and genotypes was found to be significant for yield, N uptake, and net return. At 0, 40, and 80 kg N ha⁻¹, rice genotypes Rajshree and IET8002 were at par and significantly superior to other genotypes. IET8002 outperformed Rajshree at 120 and 160 kg N ha⁻¹. None of the genotypes but Radha responded significantly to 160 kg N ha⁻¹. The grain yield and N uptake of rice genotypes Rajshree and IET

8002 at 0 kg N ha⁻¹ were superior to those of other genotypes at 40 kg N ha⁻¹. A significant increase in net return occurred up to 80 kg N ha⁻¹ for Rajshree and up to 120 kg N ha⁻¹ for IET8002. Although genotype Radha responded significantly to N application up to 160 kg N ha⁻¹, the yield and net returns obtained at that level were lower than those obtained for IET8002—even at 120 kg ha⁻¹.

Rajshree and IET8002 are superior to other genotypes for yield, N use efficiency, and net return. ■

Nitrogen use efficiency for three fertilizers in irrigated rice

A. A. Jakhrom, Sindh Agriculture University, Tando Jam, Pakistan

We evaluated the N use efficiency for ammonium sulfate, urea, and ammonium nitrate in irrigated rice grown in a saline soil.

We conducted a field experiment during the 1993 and 1994 summer seasons at Taluka Garhi Yaseen, Pakistan. The soil was clay loam in texture with a pH of 7.9, 0.09% total N, 6.5 ppm available P, 250.5 ppm exchangeable K, 90.0 ppm Ca, and 35.0 ppm Mg. The recommended fertilizer rate was 120 kg N ha⁻¹ and 33 kg P ha⁻¹. The soil had adequate exchangeable K, so K was not applied.

The experiment was laid out in a complete randomized block design with four replications. Three types of N fertilizers were used; the N level was divided into three equal splits. Before transplanting IR6 seedlings, one-third of the N was broadcast

and incorporated into the soil with a full dose of P as triple superphosphate. The remaining two-thirds was broadcast at tillering and panicle initiation.

Whole plant samples were analyzed for N concentration at tillering and heading, as were the straw and grain after harvest.

The N concentration at three physiological growth stages and in the grain significantly increased with the use of ammonium sulfate when compared with that from urea, ammonium nitrate, and the control. The low N concentration in the plant and grain from use of urea and ammonium nitrate suggests that with urea, more N is lost as ammonia because of the high soil pH, and with ammonium nitrate, anaerobic reduction causes losses of N₂O and N₂ gases (see table). Use of these two fertilizers therefore decreased grain yield.

Nitrogen use efficiency was highest with ammonium sulfate compared with urea and ammonium nitrate because of lower N losses and higher N use for grain formation (see table). ■

Effect of source of N fertilizers on flooded rice.^a

Source of N	Rate (kg N and P ha ⁻¹)	N concentration (%)				Grain yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	N efficiency use GYF-GYC ^b NS
		Tillering	Heading	Straw	Grain		
Control	0-0	0.80 c	1.10 c	0.30 c	1.50 c	2500 c	-
Ammonium sulfate	120-33	1.90 a	2.71 a	0.82 a	2.00 a	5100 a	21.67
Urea	120-33	1.60 b	2.20 b	0.65 b	1.75 b	4000 b	12.50
Ammonium nitrate	120-33	1.30 b	2.00 b	0.55 b	1.60 b	3500 b	8.33
CV %	-	9.80	8.76	10.50	11.51	12.3	-

^aData are based on means of four replications. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 0.05 level. ^bGYF = grain yield with fertilizer (kg ha⁻¹), GYC = grain yield of control (kg ha⁻¹), and NS = N applied (kg ha⁻¹).

Crop management

Response of rice hybrid PMS2 A/IR31802 to seedling vigor and nitrogen levels in Haryana, India

Hari Om, Rice Research Station (RRS), Kaul 132021, India; S. K. Katyal, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar 125004, India; and S. D. Dhiman, RRS

Heterosis in rice increases grain yield by 20% compared with the best pure lines. It is necessary, however, to assess the performance of promising hybrids at graded levels of N. Inadequate N application will not allow maximum grain yield. Excessive N may lead to excessive crop growth, creating favorable conditions for insect pests and diseases. The optimum nursery seeding rate for new hybrids also needs to be determined.

We conducted a field experiment during the 1993 and 1994 wet seasons with rice hybrid PMS2 A/IR31802 using five N levels (0, 50, 100, 150, and 200 kg ha⁻¹) and three seeding rates in the nursery (20, 40, and 60 g m⁻²). The soil of the experimental plots was clay loam with a pH of 8.1, EC 0.26 mmho cm⁻¹, and 99.6 kg available N ha⁻¹, 26.0 kg available P ha⁻¹ and 390.0 kg available K ha⁻¹.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with N levels as the mainplots and seed rates as the subplots with four replications. A uniform application 26.4 kg P ha⁻¹ and 25 kg ZnSO₄ ha⁻¹ was broadcast before transplanting, which was done in the last week of June at a spacing of 20 × 15 cm with 1 seedling hill⁻¹. N was topdressed in